

MEDICAL SCIENCES

EFFICIENCY AND AESTHETIC CHARACTERISTICS OF CERAMIC VENEERS

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Abstract

This article reviews the efficacy and aesthetic properties of ceramic veneers. Various types of ceramic materials, including lithium disilicate, zirconia, feldspathic, and glass ceramics, are analyzed with a focus on their mechanical and aesthetic properties. Special attention is given to the durability of ceramic veneers, complication rates, and patient satisfaction based on clinical studies. The limitations of ceramic veneers, particularly related to material fragility, the complexity of enamel preparation procedures, and their impact on tooth functionality, are also discussed. The combination of strength and aesthetic properties in lithium disilicate ceramics has shown advantages over zirconia ceramics, though further data on long-term efficacy are required. Feldspathic and glass ceramics exhibit some limitations, particularly regarding technical complications. The article concludes that additional research is needed to optimize material selection and treatment protocols.

Keywords: ceramic veneers, lithium disilicate ceramics, aesthetic dentistry, durability of restorations, adhesive fixation, aesthetic properties.

Introduction

Aesthetic dentistry plays a crucial role in modern medical practice, facilitating both the restoration of dental functions and the enhancement of dental appearance. The placement of dental veneers is one such method of aesthetic correction, allowing for the restoration of tooth shape, color, and alignment with minimal invasive procedures [1]. The global market for dental veneers in 2023 was valued at USD 2,36 billion, and it is projected to reach USD 3,88 billion by 2031, growing at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 7,4% from 2024 to 2031 [2]. The growing demand for aesthetic dental procedures has contributed to the rapid expansion of this market. Advances in material science have significantly enhanced the durability and aesthetic properties of veneers, making them a popular choice among patients seeking to improve their dental aesthetics.

Modern ceramic veneers (CV) are typically fabricated from lithium disilicate (LDC), zirconia ceramics (ZC), glass ceramics, or feldspathic materials [3]. The installation of CV involves minimal enamel preparation, which helps preserve a significant volume of natural tooth structure. In the context of CV application,

the main concerns are durability, aesthetics, and the effect on tooth functionality. Durability depends on the mechanical strength, wear resistance, and adhesive bonding quality. Aesthetic properties encompass color stability, compatibility with the natural shade of teeth, and patient satisfaction. The functional impact of veneers is assessed by their ability to maintain chewing efficiency, minimize the risk of pathological processes, and improve the overall dental appearance of the patient.

The aim of this study is to analyze the efficiency and aesthetic properties CV based on available literature. This review will assess modern approaches to the use of CV and systematize data on the durability of various ceramic materials. This article will help identify both the advantages and limitations of this restorative technique.

Main part

When selecting a ceramic material for dental applications, it is essential to consider its properties, as well as the intended use area [4]. Different ceramic materials exhibit specific characteristics that influence their suitability for particular clinical indications (Table 1).

Table 1.

Comparison of the main materials for veneers

Type ceramics	Strength on bending (MPa)	Aesthetic characteristics	Main region applications
Lithium disilicate	350–400	High color stability	Restorations in high load zones
Zirconium	up to 1000	Moderate, lower transparency	Restorations requiring high wear resistance
Feldspathic	approximately 120	High visual appeal	Restorations for anterior teeth
Glass ceramics	160–220	High transparency, color stability	Aesthetic restorations, particularly for anterior teeth

The aesthetic properties of veneer restorations are evaluated using both subjective and objective methods [5]. Subjective methods often involve questionnaires and surveys to gauge patient satisfaction with the restoration's appearance. These studies provide insight into

how well the restoration meets patient expectations. Objective methods include spectrophotometric measurements to accurately assess color stability and the alignment of veneer shades with natural tooth colors. Digital technologies such as photographic and scanning

systems enhance the precision of aesthetic assessments and enable documentation of treatment outcomes. Visual analog scales (VAS) are also commonly employed to standardize aesthetic evaluations and facilitate comparison across studies.

Recent studies affirm the high aesthetic and durability outcomes of CV. In 2024, a patient satisfaction survey conducted at the Lema Clinic Dental Clinic (Turkey) revealed that over 90% of patients reported a significant improvement in the aesthetics of their smile post-veneer application, citing improvements in color, shape, and alignment of their teeth. Additionally, patients noted increased self-confidence due to the enhanced appearance of their teeth, with high satisfaction

also reported for the durability and comfort of the veneers, which were praised for their natural feel and resistance to discoloration with proper care.

In a study by Yılmaz Umut Aslan, PhD, et al., the long-term clinical efficacy and survival of pressed lithium disilicate (LD) glass-ceramic veneers were assessed through retrospective analysis spanning 5, 10, 15, and 20 years [7]. The study covered 413 veneers placed in the anterior and posterior regions of 51 patients. The average follow-up period was $11,33 \pm 4,85$ years. The results indicated high veneer survival rates: 98% after 5 years, 95% after 10 years, 91% after 15 years, and 87% after 20 years (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Durability of LD CV[7]

The primary complications observed included chipping (1,45%) and detachment (2,18%), while no cases of secondary caries were reported. Esthetic parameters such as color matching and anatomical shape were rated highly, achieving a score of 0 according to the United States Public Health Service (USPHS). Patient satisfaction was 97% for functional outcomes and 98% for aesthetic outcomes. The study highlights the reliability and long-term effectiveness of LD veneers in restoring dental aesthetics.

In a systematic review by Patrick Klein et al., a study was conducted to evaluate the durability and complication rates of veneers made from various materials, including feldspathic, leucite-reinforced glass ceramics (LRGC), LDC, and ceramics, with follow-up periods categorized as short-term (1-3 years), medium-term (4-6 years), and long-term (≥ 7 years) [8]. A total of 29 clinical studies were analyzed, encompassing 7753 veneers in 986 patients with follow-up periods ranging from 1 to 20 years. The short-term survival rate was 97,76% (95% confidence interval (CI): 96,42%-99,01%), medium-term survival rate was 97,12% (95% CI: 95,22%-98,79%), and long-term survival rate was 96,05% (95% CI: 93,87%-97,46%). Among the materials, LDC exhibited the lowest complication rates: technical complications 6,1% (95% CI: 0,60%-16,60%), aesthetic complications 1,9% (95% CI: 0,45%-11,72%), and biological complications 0,45% (95% CI: 0,12%-1,16%) at a mean follow-up of 10,4 years. Feldspathic and SCL materials demonstrated slightly higher complication rates: technical complica-

tions were 41,48% and 29,87%, respectively, while biological complications were 6,51% and 4,4%. Ceramic crowns showed 100% survival with no complications in the short term; however, long-term data are still lacking. The primary conclusion of the study is that CK is a reliable and minimally invasive dental restoration method, and LDC is recommended as the material with the lowest risk of complications for long-term use. Further studies are necessary to evaluate the long-term efficacy of ceramic crowns veneers.

Limitations of the use of KV

Despite the advantages, CV have several limitations that should be considered when planning restorative treatments. Ceramic materials are brittle, making them susceptible to mechanical damage under localized overloads, such as strong chewing pressure, sudden temperature changes, or impacts from hard objects (instruments, adjacent teeth, or dentures) [9]. The effectiveness and durability of CV largely depend on the area of application and how well the selected material meets functional and aesthetic requirements. Feldspathic or glass ceramics are preferable for the restoration of anterior teeth; however, their use is limited by lower bending strength. For molars and premolars, which are subject to greater chewing forces, LDC or ceramic crowns are the optimal choices. However, ceramic crowns are less aesthetically appealing due to its reduced transparency, limiting its use in the smile zone.

The installation of CV requires precise and minimally invasive enamel preparation. Any deviation from established protocols, including excessive removal of hard dental tissue or inadequate surface treatment, can

result in reduced adhesion, excessive damage to dental tissue, and less conservative treatment outcomes.

Discussion

The use of CV for restoring both aesthetic and functional characteristics of teeth is a reliable and effective method. Analysis of the available data suggests that the material selection for the fabrication of veneers directly influences their durability and clinical effectiveness. Among the materials, LDC demonstrates the most balanced combination of preservation, mechanical strength, and aesthetic appeal, making it the preferred material for restorations in both the anterior and posterior regions of the dentition. Retrospective analyses of cases using LDC indicate a high level of veneer preservation over extended periods (up to 20 years), supported by the material's stability and a low incidence of complications such as chipping and detachment. Additionally, the absence of secondary caries in the studied patient cohort underscores the high quality of adhesive fixation and the biocompatibility of this material.

A systematic review of literature data confirms that all types of ceramic materials show high short-term and medium-term survival rates. However, LDC consistently demonstrates the lowest incidence of technical, aesthetic, and biological complications, emphasizing its significant potential for long-term clinical use. Conversely, the higher incidence of complications with feldspathic and SCL veneers indicates their limited applicability, primarily in the restoration of anterior teeth where the mechanical load is minimal.

The limitations of ceramic crowns are mainly related to their moderate aesthetic appeal and the lack of long-term data regarding their clinical efficacy. However, short-term studies indicate that ceramic crowns perform well without complications, suggesting high potential when strict protocols for fixation and material selection are adhered to. These findings underscore the necessity for further research to assess the long-term efficacy of ceramic crowns.

Conclusions

The use of CV represents a reliable and minimally invasive method for restoring both the aesthetics and functionality of teeth. The analysis of available literature confirms the high durability and aesthetic appeal of materials such as LDC, which offer an optimal combination of strength, biocompatibility, and color stabil-

ity. However, the limitations related to material fragility and the technical complexity of installation procedures highlight the need for strict adherence to treatment protocols. Long-term clinical data are necessary to confirm the clinical effectiveness of ceramic crowns. Further research is required to optimize material selection and establish standardized protocols for the use of CV in various clinical scenarios.

References

1. Durán Ojeda G, Bresser RA, Wendler M, Gresnigt MMM. Ceramic partial laminate veneers in anterior teeth: A literature review. *J Prosthodont Res.* 2024;68(2):246-254.
2. Dental Veneers Market Size by Product, by Application, by Geography, Competitive Landscape, and Forecasts. Text: electronic. URL: <https://www.marketresearchintellect.com/ru/product/global-dental-veneers-market-size-forecast/> (date of access: 27.11.2024).
3. Araujo E, Perdigão J. Anterior Veneer Restorations - An Evidence-based Minimal-Intervention Perspective. *J Adhes Dent.* 2021;23(2):91-110.
4. Villalobos-Tinoco J, Jurado CA, Sanchez-Hernandez RA, Elgreatly A, Alshabib A, Tsujimoto A. Injectable Flowable Resin-based Composite Veneers Prior to Ceramic Veneers. *Opera Dent.* 2023;48(4):351-357.
5. Kelleher M. Myths and falls about ceramic veneers. *Br Dent J* 2024;236(5):359.
6. Dental Veneers Satisfaction Survey. Text: electronic. URL: <https://lemaclinic.com/ru/> (date of access: 27.11.2024).
7. Aslan YU, Uludamar A, Özkan Y. Clinical performance of pressable glass-ceramic veneers after 5, 10, 15, and 20 years: A retrospective case series study. *J Esthet Restor Dent.* 2019;31(5):415-422.
8. Klein P, Spitznagel FA, Zembic A, Prott LS, Pieralli S, Bongaerts B, Metzendorf MI, Langner R, Giertmuehlen PC. Survival and Complication Rates of Feldspathic, Leucite-Reinforced, Lithium Disilicate and Zirconia Ceramic Laminate Veneers: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *J Esthet Restor Dent.* 2024.
9. Alhazzawi TF. Clinical Survival Rate and Laboratory Failure of Dental Veneers: A Narrative Literature Review. *J Function Biomater.* 2024;15(5):131.